

USING GENRE BASED APPROACH IN ONLINE LEARNING TO IMPROVE STUDENTS' WRITING SKILL IN WRITING ANALYTICAL EXPOSITION TEXT

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Abstract: This study is aimed to finding out whether there is a significant difference towards students' writing ability who are taught by process genre-based approach and those who are taught by using non-PGBA learning through online learning. The result of this study showed that (1) there were significant effects of process genre-based approach through online learning on students' writing skills in analytical exposition text. The result of the pre-test to post-test difference test using the Independent T-test generated the Asymp value. Sig (2 – tailed) is 0.001 ($p < 0.05$), so, that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted, it continue with the result of the effect size test using Pearson correlation r , and obtained $r = 0.411$ (16.94%) and categorized in medium effect. (2) The aspects of writing in the experimental group (PGBA); The percentage of Organization (16.08%) and Spelling (81.3%) scaled with excellent criteria. Meanwhile 4 from 6 aspect; for the Idea and Development is (23.50%), Vocabulary (11.91%), Sentence Structure (14.83%), Capitalization and Punctuation (7.25%) have scaled into good criteria. Then, the difference score (23%). The difference score here figures out the students' scores not achieved maximally.

INTRODUCTION

Even though students can write, read, and listen well in foreign language classes, the writing seems to be the hardest skill to learn. A writer should think about mechanics, grammar, writing style, and the difficulties of communicating what needs to be said. According to McCarrier, A., Pinnell, G. S. (2000), they stated that there are several processes in writing. Before beginning to write, a writer must consider the intent of the writing, the intended reader, and the type or method of writing that will be used to convey the message. Then, when composing, technical and grammatical precision come into play. A writer reflects and evaluates during the process as the final step. If the text is more than a few words long, the writer rereads as he or she goes, viewing each sentence as a component of a larger text.

The objective of writing is to produce a kind of writing text. An analytical exposition text is one of the texts learnt in the eleventh year of high school. Analytical text is an argumentative text containing the view of the writer on a controversial subject. Analytical exposition text is a part of expository writing in kind of text genre. According to Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan Indonesia, (2013) there four basic competences in learning writing; 1) transactional text, 2) formal letter, 3) analytical exposition text, and 4) personal letter.

Genre Based Approach provides the features of similar group of text based on the social context of the creation and use (Hyland, 2003:21). So, the use of this approach can help the students to create a selected kind of written or oral text. As Feez, S. & Joyce, (1998:40) describe that Genre

Based Approach is an approach used in teaching language skill about the structure and grammar features of spoken and written texts.

In Addition, mind map has a natural organizational structure that radiates from the centre and use lines, symbols, key words, colour and images according to simple, brain-friendly concepts (Buzan 2005). A mind mapping converts a long list of monotonous information into a colourful, memorable and highly organized diagram that works in line with your brain’s natural way of doing things.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Graham et al. (2012) claimed that writing is a useful tool to read, connect and express oneself. It is an integral part of educational, social, social and municipal communication. It's used in different fields, which in many situations will facilitate citizens. In several areas of our everyday lives we find writings that have meaningful functions. Kristin Lems, Leah D. Miller (2010) stated it includes a thought process that requires a deep knowledge and practice to avoid misunderstandings between writer and reader. It includes thinking processes which involve an extensive understanding and practice. Writers are typically split with the readers at various times and locations. In addition Nunan (1991) stated writers must also make inferences about the appropriate information of readers, determine what to add, remove and predict future difficulties for readers. Writing is perceived by second language students as the most difficult master's skill. The problem is to create and coordinate ideas and translate them into a legible text. Richards & Renandya (2002) stated that the skills of writing are very complex because writers are concerned with greater planning and organizational skills, also with lower levels like grammar, punctuation, word choice, etc.

b. Writing opens opportunities to learn

Writing as a discovery process gives authors the ability to discover concepts and viewpoints. It can understand religions and values. In addition, the writing process extends the experience of authors and changes their thought. It also leads to the efficient generalization, sentence and rational thinking.

c. Writing nurtures personal development

Writing increases trust, handles the self-affairs of authors, monitors self- progress, recognizes beliefs, develops goals, specifies concerns and succeeds. They will evolve and mature as writers acquire knowledge. Also, writing can help authors have certain outlets in their lives. The ability to communicate well.

d. Writing helps to establish relationships

It helps preserve relationships with people or society by being able to write well and to create friendly written voices. Positive relationships can effectually build on the ability to choose positive terms, to remove negative ideas and to polish sentences.

e. Writing helps school and workplace success

For college and workplace success, writing is important. The ability to write well would help students to try to learn and share ideas. In order to evaluate their awareness, it is necessary not only to learn a language, but also for all subjects. In this work, writing allows you to think more about and write about real issues, including papers, e-mails, offers, etc.

4. Problem in Writing

According to (Byrne 1993), there are some difficulties related to writing; psychology, linguistic and cognitive difficulties. The first is the psychological difficulty of how to express the idea. According to

(Trotman 2006) writing is having a message and communicating it successfully to others. Students need ideas and then arrange them in a good manner in order to deliver the message to the reader successfully. The second difficulty is dealing with linguistic. There is linguistic difficulty in that the language used in written language. The written language differs from the spoken language. In written language, there are lies grammatical rules that should be considered. The third difficulty is related to cognitive difficulty in which the students must organize their ideas on text with signal words to make the sequence of paragraphs well arranged.

Methodology

These studies are quantitative research. It can be classified as quasi experimental study. The experimental study is the best way to determine the relationship between variables of cause and effect (Fraenkel, Jack R., Wallen 2009) The population of this research is the XI grade students of in academic year of 2021/2022. Each classes consists of 35 to 36 students. The samples of this research are two classes (Class XI MIPA 1 and Class XI MIPA 3).

Result and Discussion

The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of applying the process genre-based approach learning model to analytical exposition text learning in English lessons on the learning outcomes of eleventh graders of SMAN 1 Purworejo in the odd semester of the 2021/2022 academic year. To answer the research objectives, statistical tests were carried out with IBM SPSS 26 for Windows. In accordance with the opinion of Offirstson (2014: 83) that before carrying out statistical analysis, testing the difference in scores from the pre-test and post-test results first to test for normality and homogeneity.

The results of the normality test in the study showed that all variables were normal. All normal data, namely a) the pre-test score of the experimental group with a sig value. (2-tailed) 0.200; b) The experimental group's post-test score with a sig. (2-tailed) 0.200; c) The control group's post-test score with sig. (2-tailed) 0.200; and d) The difference between the score of the control group and the value of sig. (2-tailed) 0.184, pre-test score of the control group with a sig value. (2-tailed) 0.200 and the difference in the score of the experimental group with a value of sig.(2-tailed) 0.200. Thus, the next analysis uses non-parametric analysis where the analysis does not require the assumption of a normal data distribution.

The prerequisite test used next is the homogeneity test. The results of the homogeneity test using Levene Statistics show that the variance of the data is homogeneous with a mean significance value above 0.05, which is 0.006. Likewise, if the basis of measurement is the median, the significance number of 0.941 is still greater than 0.05. So, it can be said that the data comes from populations that have the same variance.

The results of the statistical test on the student's initial ability test showed that there was no difference in the initial ability as indicated by the Asymp price. Sig. (2-tailed) is 0.660, meaning that the initial abilities of the control group and experimental group students are not different or the same, so it is possible to make comparisons. In addition, the interpretation of Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) according to Field, (2009) he stated that If the value is less than .05 then the two groups are significantly different.

The results of this study are in accordance with the research hypothesis which shows the influence of the process-genre-based approach learning model on learning outcomes. This effect can be seen from the difference in pre-test and post-test scores between the control and experimental groups which have a significant difference with the Sig. (2-tailed) value of 0.001 or $p < 0.05$ on the test results with the Independent T-test. Based on these results, H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. That is, there is a significant difference between the difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of the experimental group and the control group. The results of calculations using the formula $(O_2 - O_1) - (O_4 - O_3)$ also show that there is an influence of the process-genre based approach learning model on student learning outcomes by obtaining positive results of 11.04.

The control group and the experimental group experienced a positive increase, only in the control group the pre-test and post-test scores were not significantly related. This is shown from the results of the pre-test and post-test score correlation test which obtained a positive correlation coefficient value of 0.251 and a sig. (2 – tailed) 0.181 in the control group. The significance value between pre-test and post-test is more than 0.05 ($0.251 > 0.05$), meaning that there is no significant relationship between pre-test and post-test scores. The positive correlation coefficient indicates a positive relationship, meaning that the higher the pre-test, the higher the post-test. While in the experimental group the correlation coefficient value obtained is 0.551 and the value of sig. (2 – tailed) 0.002. The significance value is $0.002 < 0.05$, meaning that there is a significant relationship between the pre-test and post-test in the experimental group. The positive correlation coefficient indicates that there is a positive relationship, meaning that the higher the pre-test, the higher the post-test score.

The results of the Paired T-test obtained the Asymp. Sig (2-tailed) 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) in the control group. Paired T-test results show that the probability value < 0.05 , then H_0 is accepted. That is, there is a difference in learning outcomes between the pre-test and post-test scores in the control group. Then Asymp. Sig (2-tailed) was 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) in the experimental group. Paired T-test results show that the probability value < 0.05 , then H_0 is rejected. That is, there is a difference in learning outcomes between the pre-test and post-test scores in the experimental group. The results of the calculation of the effect of the treatment in the control group using the conventional model of $r = 5.479$ and the percentage of the treatment effect of 50.86% which is included in the small category, while the magnitude of the treatment in the experimental group using the process-genre based approach learning model with $r = 15.817$ and the percentage of treatment effect is 89.61% which is included in the High category. From these results, it can be seen that the process-genre-based approach learning model has a greater influence than the conventional model.

The use of the process-genre based approach learning model has an influence of 89.61% on learning outcomes, while the remaining 10.39% is the influence of other variables outside the variables studied. Likewise in the control group, the non-PGBA has an effect of 50.86% on learning outcomes, while the remaining 49.11% is the influence of other variables. The other variables include 1) Student psychological factors, such as interest or motivation. 2) Community environmental factors, such as friends. 3) Family environmental factors, namely family background and parental education, and 6) School time factor (Suwardi, 2012:6). Based on the above results, the process-genre-based approach

and lecture learning models have an effect on learning outcomes, although the effect on the experimental group is greater than that of the control group. Treatment is the cause of improvement, as long as there is no interference from other variables (Fitz & Davidson, 2012: 193). The process-genre based approach learning model was used as a treatment in the experimental group and was not carried out in the control group, but in this study, lectures also had an effect or the control group also experienced an increase. The post-test in the control group was conducted not on the same day as the delivery of the material. The learning activities in the control group were different from the learning activities carried out in the experimental group. Learning in the control group uses a conventional learning model where students follow the lesson by listening to the teacher's explanation directly. Meanwhile, the experimental group used a process-genre-based approach learning model where Hyland (2003) presents the cycle model of Genre-based teaching process that proceeds from Modeling, Joint Construction, and Independent Construction of text. In Genre-based writing process, students start with BKOF, MOT, JCOT and ICOT.

Based on the calculation obtained by using the effect size for all aspect in writing, according to the table above it can be seen that the aspect of content has largest effect than the other aspect. The percentage of content is (23.37%). But, for the organization (16.08%), and vocabulary (11.25%), were in same category. Those aspect belongs to medium category. On the other hand, the writing aspect of grammar (14.91%), and mechanic (11.93%). In this case, it means that learning writing analytical exposition text using the Genre Based Approach class XI science students at SMA N 1 Purworejo has a major influence on students' writing abilities in the aspect of content. Fortunately, the other aspects include organization, vocabulary, grammar and mechanic. Which have the same category in medium categorization.

While the lowest aspect can be owned by the writing aspect related to spelling. In the experimental class, students actively interact such as doing questions and answers with their friends and also with the teacher. The percentage increase in the mean pre-test and post-test scores in the experimental class was 89.61%. This is in accordance with opinion of (Darmadi., 2017: 383) that learning outcomes will increase if there is interaction in the learning process. Meanwhile, students in the control group tended to sit quietly in their respective chairs to listen to the explanation of the material, but the control group also experienced an increase. The percentage increase in the control group was 50.86%.

CONCLUSION

The results of the analysis of statistical tests on the difference between the pre-test and post-test scores in the control and experimental groups showed sig. (2-tailed) is 0.001 or $p < 0.05$, so H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. This means that there is a difference between the pre-test and post-test scores. The learning model process-genre based approach influences the learning outcomes of eleventh graders in learning English to write analytical exposition texts. This can be seen from the analysis of the mean score improvement percentage calculation, that experimental class reached 43.67%. Then The inquiry learning model has a medium effect on student learning outcomes. It can be seen from big data analysis the effect size of the learning model inquiry on learning outcomes with a value of $r = 0.411$ and the percentage of influence by 16.94%.

The six aspects of writing in experimental was better than control group. In the term to know which the aspect that give the most significant effect in improving the student's writing skill to write analytical exposition text. The answer was generated through effect size testing (See page 56). Based on the calculation obtained by using the effect size

for all aspect in writing, according to the table 4.10, the aspect of content has largest effect than the other aspect. The percentage of ideas and development is (23.50%). Meanwhile, for the organization (16.92%), vocabulary (7.54%), sentence structure (14.83%), capitalization and punctuation (7.25%), spelling (8.13%), and different score (21.83%). The different score here figures out the students score not achieved maximally.

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